

Highlights

Conceptual Design of Electrodynamic Multi Tether System for Self-propelled Jovian Capture

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- Electrodynamic tethers are studied for propellant-less Jovian capture of a spacecraft
- An analysis of the structural, thermal, and relativistic constraints is performed
- A multi tether configuration is shown to be required and is used for the design
- An optimal solution to Lambert's problem is selected for the interplanetary transfer
- The tether system can be switched to power generation mode after the capture

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Abstract

Space missions in the environments of the outer planets require a large amount of propellant or assistant flybys. Moreover, the quadratic decrease of the radiation intensity with the distance from the sun makes solar panels less convenient as power source. Electrodynamic tether (EDT) technology is receiving increasing attention since it allows for obtaining both power and propulsion profiting from the high magnetic field and plasma density in the proximity of the giant planets. In particular, it has been shown that a self-propelled vehicle with a single EDT could be captured by Jupiter, were it not for the relativistic effects in the electron collection and the overheating of the tether due to the interaction with the environment. Here, we show that a multi EDT (MEDT) propulsion system can be used to circumvent these limitations. The suitable number, shape, and length of the tethers, depending on the size of the vehicle, are selected by structural and thermal analysis. A possible MEDT-propelled mission to Jupiter is described, including the design of the interplanetary trajectory, the orbital insertion, and the subsequent orbits around the planet. The results obtained demonstrate that such a bare MEDT system is a feasible option to provide propulsion and power in outer planets environments.

Keywords:

Electrodynamic tether, Interplanetary missions, Orbit insertion, Jovian environment

1. Introduction

Since its first exploration by *Pioneer* space probes in the early 70s, Jupiter has been the object of increasing scientific interest. In particular, the search for life in one of its moons [1, 2, 3] represents a major goal for *Europa Clipper* [4] and *Jupiter Icy Moons Orbiter* [5]. The design of such missions requires the optimized use of fuel and multiple gravity-assist events for the interplanetary trajectory. The mass of the vehicle has to be minimized accordingly. However, the shortage of solar radiation near the outer planets has to be compensated either by increasing the size of the solar arrays, such as for the *Juno* mission [6], or by using alternative sources of power, such as heavy radioisotope thermoelectric generators [7], in both cases affecting the mass.

A possible strategy to address these challenges may be the use of Electrodynamic Tethers (EDTs), since they may allow for self-propulsion and power generation in the proximity of the giant planets by absorbing energy from the ambient magnetic field and plasma [8]. EDT technology has been the subject of intense research since the experiments with the Tethered Satellite System-1, TSS-1R [9]. In particular, the conditions for their possible use in the Jovian environment have been studied in Refs. [10, 11]. An attractive application would be the use

of EDT self-propulsion for the orbit insertion [12, 13], however, the actual simulations show that this could only be possible with tether length $L_t \gtrsim 20$ or 50 km, depending on the inclination and radius of periapsis of the incoming hyperbola. Unfortunately, EDTs of such size would face several challenges. As argued in Ref. [14], relativistic effects produced in such long Langmuir probes would affect the penetration length of energetic electrons into the EDT, thus reducing the electron collection. Additional constraints arise from the thermal and structural considerations that will be discussed here.

To circumvent these limitations, we propose the possibility of using a multi-EDT (MEDT) system with shorter tethers for obtaining both the self-propelled Jovian capture, and a source of power generation after the target orbit is reached. The structural, thermal, and relativistic constraints are taken into account to select the number, shape and length of the tethers, depending on the size of the vehicle. A mathematical formulation based on the available experimental data is also introduced for a realistic modeling of the ambient magnetic field and the plasma density around Jupiter. The orbital computations are then performed by using Gauss variational equations for the non-singular equinoctial variables. We then describe a possible MEDT-propelled mission to Jupiter, including the interplanetary trajectory, the orbital insertion, and the subsequent orbits around the planet. The MEDT is used for propulsion until the desired orbit around Jupiter is achieved. Afterwards, by connecting a suitable resistance to the circuit, the MEDT can provide both propulsive

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power for station keeping, and electric power for the scientific instrumentation on board.

Fig. 1 shows a conceptual design of a spacecraft with MEDT system for Jovian capture. The different elements and their characteristics will be analyzed in Sec. 7. A solar panel array has been included to generate power during the interplanetary trajectory. Once the vehicle is inserted in the desired Jovian orbit, the required power for the scientific payload and platform can be supplied by the MEDT.

Figure 1: Schematic design of a spacecraft with MEDT system for Jovian capture.

2. Principle of operation of the EDTs

An EDT is a long and thin conductive wire in which an electric current is induced when it moves through a magnetic field in presence of a plasma. These conditions can be found in the plasma-magnetospheres of the Earth, Jupiter, Saturn, Uranus, and Neptune [12]. An EDT moving in the planetary magnetic field \mathbf{B} experiences an electric field

$$\mathbf{E}_m = \mathbf{v}_{\text{rel}} \times \mathbf{B}, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{v}_{rel} is the relative velocity between the spacecraft and the planetary magnetic field \mathbf{B} . The interaction of this field with the ambient plasma induces the flow of a current in the tether, whose average value can be written as

$$\mathbf{I}_{\text{avg}} = I_0 \left(1 - \frac{2}{5} \Lambda\right) \Lambda^{3/2} \hat{\mathbf{u}}, \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{u}}$ is a unit vector identifying the orientation of the tether, and Λ is the distance of the zero-bias point from the anode divided by the tether length L_t [15, 16, 17, 12]. Hereafter, we will assume $\Lambda = 1$, corresponding to the cathode being the zero-bias point, in order to maximize the current. We have performed a trade-off study of the tether cross section taking into account the deploy technique and the relativistic, thermal, and structural constraints that will be discussed in Sections 5 and 6, and found that the preferred configuration is circular. The constant

I_0 is a function of the tether geometry and the environmental conditions. It depends on the diameter D and the length L_t of the round tether, and on the ambient electron density N_e and the electric field \mathbf{E}_m , as follows,

$$I_0 = \frac{2}{3} D q_e N_e L_t^{3/2} \sqrt{2(\mathbf{E}_m \cdot \hat{\mathbf{u}}) \left(\frac{q_e}{m_e}\right)}, \quad (3)$$

with q_e and m_e being the charge and mass of the electron, respectively [15, 16, 17, 12].

Assuming uniform density along the tether, the Lorentz force produced by the magnetic field of the planet is

$$\mathbf{F}_L = L_t \mathbf{I}_{\text{avg}} \times \mathbf{B}. \quad (4)$$

The induced current can also be used to generate power, while the Lorentz force is a source of self-propulsion. In contrast to traditional thrusters and power sources, EDTs can then provide energy as a result of the electromagnetic interaction with the plasma and the magnetic field of the target planet.

3. Jovian environment

EDT-based systems can be of special interest for missions aimed at orbiting Jupiter [12] and at searching for life in its Galilean moons. The plasma-magnetosphere of the giant planet has been studied both with the observation of its synchrotron radiation from the Earth, and with in situ data collection by the space probes *Pioneer 10*, *Pioneer 11*, *Voyager 1*, and *Voyager 2*. These data have been analyzed in a comprehensive study by [18], whose results for the dependence of the electron density N_e of the plasmasphere in the equatorial plane, as a function of the distance from the center of Jupiter, are given in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Density of the electrons in Jupiter equatorial plane, as a function of the distance from the center of planet. Model based on [18].

Following [18], the electron density in the proximity of Jupiter can be modeled as,

$$N_e(r, \lambda, l) = N_0 \exp \left[\frac{r_0}{r} - \left(\frac{r}{H_0} - 1 \right)^2 (\lambda - \lambda_c)^2 \right], \quad (5)$$

for a distance to the center of the planet in the range $1.0 < r < 3.8 R_J$, where

$$\lambda_c = (\tan \alpha) \cos (l - l_0), \quad (6)$$

$N_0 = 4.65 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ is the electron density at the surface of the planet, and $r_0 = 7.68 R_J$, $H_0 = 1.0 R_J$, and $\alpha = 7^\circ$ are experimental scale factors defined in Ref. [18] (R_J being the radius of Jupiter). As location variables, λ and l are the latitude and longitude, respectively, in Jupiter System III reference frame [18]. Hereafter, an equatorial orbit is chosen in order to maximize the vector product of the magnetic field and the relative velocity. This model is more accurate than other used in previous studies of EDT self-propulsion around Jupiter, such as in [12], where the radial dependence of the electron density was ignored.

Following [19], Io's internal magnetic field will be neglected, and Jupiter's magnetic field will be modeled with a dipole approximation,

$$\mathbf{B} = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \frac{1}{r^3} [3(\mathbf{M} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}})\hat{\mathbf{r}} - \mathbf{M}] = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \frac{|\mathbf{M}|}{r^3} [3(\hat{\mathbf{M}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}})\hat{\mathbf{r}} - \hat{\mathbf{M}}], \quad (7)$$

where $\mu_0 = 4\pi \times 10^{-7} \text{ H/m}$ is the permeability constant, \mathbf{M} is the magnetic dipole moment vector, and $\hat{\mathbf{M}}$ is a unit vector aligned with \mathbf{M} and with the South-North direction of the Jovian magnetic poles. In our simulations, $\hat{\mathbf{M}}$ will be used as the third axis of an inertial coordinate system centered in Jupiter. Using a set of Keplerian orbital elements for describing the position of the satellite [20], $\hat{\mathbf{M}}$ can be written as,

$$\hat{\mathbf{M}} = \sin(\omega + \nu) \sin i \hat{\mathbf{r}} + \cos(\omega + \nu) \sin i \hat{\boldsymbol{\nu}} + \cos i \hat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}, \quad (8)$$

where ν , ω , and i are the true anomaly, the argument of perijove, and the inclination, respectively. The orthogonal unit vectors, $\hat{\mathbf{r}}$, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\nu}}$, and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}$ correspond to the instant radial, tangent, and normal directions to the plane of the orbit, respectively.

The results of Fig. 2, together with the $\sim 1/r^3$ dependence of the magnetic field, make the resulting electromagnetic force on the tethers to be vanishing small except in a relatively small radial region around Jupiter. We shall see how this fact can be used for producing the orbit insertion.

As shown in Ref. [14], the tether potential (ignoring ohmic and orientation losses) can be approximated as $\Phi \approx v_{rel} B L_t$. The ratio $\beta \equiv \frac{q_e \Phi}{m_e c^2}$ can then be used to assess the importance of relativistic effects in the electron collection [14]. These quantities can be computed for the configuration described in Sec. 7. The resulting values, $\Phi \approx 0.14 \text{ MV}$ and $\beta \approx 0.246$, correspond to the orbital-motion-limited regime in which relativistic effects are negligible. Therefore, the MEDT system that will be described in Sec. 7 will automatically satisfy the relativistic constraints established in Ref. [14].

4. Dynamical equations

The Lorentz force per unit mass produced by the interaction of the tether with the environment, $\Delta \mathbf{a} = \mathbf{F}_L/m$, can be added to the propagator of the orbit of the spacecraft as a perturbation,

$$\ddot{\mathbf{r}} = -\mu \frac{\mathbf{r}}{r^3} + \Delta \mathbf{a}, \quad (9)$$

where $\mu = GM_J = 1.26686534 \cdot 10^{17} \text{ [m}^3/\text{s}^2]$ is the standard gravitational parameter of Jupiter. Taking into account Eqs. (4), (7), and (8), we obtain

$$\mathbf{F}_L = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \frac{|\mathbf{M}|}{r^3} \sum_k L_{t,k} I_k [\cos i \hat{\boldsymbol{\nu}} - \cos(\omega + \nu) \sin i \hat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}], \quad (10)$$

where $\sum_k L_{t,k} I_k$ is the sum of products of the lengths and induced currents of all the tethers.

Fig. 3 shows the radial dependence of the Lorentz force acting on a single EDT, depending on the length of the tether. The spacecraft is assumed to move in the equatorial plane of Jupiter's magnetic field, with the EDT aligned with the radial direction. The different curves refer to different values of the length of the tether. The force increases sharply with the length L_t of the tether, with a dependence that is $\propto L_t^{5/2}$, as shown in Eqs. (2), (3), and (4). For this reason, EDT in the range from 10 to 50 km [12], or even 100 km [13], have been considered in the literature. EDT systems shorter than the meter scale have only been proposed as possible mechanism for the attitude control of chip satellites in Ref. [21].

Figure 3: Lorentz Force F_L acting on an EDT moving in the equatorial plane of the magnetic field of Jupiter, as a function of the distance from the center of the planet. The tether is assumed to be aligned in the radial direction. The different curves refer to different values of the length of the tether.

It is convenient to express the perturbing acceleration along the perifocal axes $\hat{\mathbf{r}}$, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\nu}}$, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}$. Taking into account Eqs. (9) and (10), we obtain,

$$\Delta a_r = 0, \quad (11)$$

$$\Delta a_\nu = \frac{1}{m} \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \frac{|\mathbf{M}|}{r^3} \sum_k L_{t,k} I_k \cos i, \quad (12)$$

$$\Delta a_\omega = -\frac{1}{m} \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \frac{|\mathbf{M}|}{r^3} \sum_k L_{t,k} I_k \cos(\omega + \nu) \sin i. \quad (13)$$

The evolution of the orbital elements will be studied with Gauss variational method. Since the chosen trajectories evolve in the equatorial plane of the Jupiter-centered inertial frame described in Sec. 3, the simulations will be performed using a set of non-singular equinoctial elements, p , f , g , h , k , L , which are related to the classical elements e , a , i , Ω , ω , and ν , as follows [22],

$$p = a(1 - e^2), \quad (14)$$

$$f = e \cos \omega + \Omega, \quad (15)$$

$$g = e \sin \omega + \Omega, \quad (16)$$

$$h = \tan i/2 \cos \Omega, \quad (17)$$

$$k = \tan i/2 \sin \Omega, \quad (18)$$

$$L = \Omega + \omega + \nu. \quad (19)$$

Gauss variational equations for the modified equinoctial elements are [23],

$$\frac{dp}{dt} = \frac{2p}{w} \sqrt{\frac{p}{\mu}} \Delta a_\nu, \quad (20)$$

$$\frac{df}{dt} = \sqrt{\frac{p}{\mu}} \left[\Delta a_r \sin L + [(w+1) \cos L + f] \frac{\Delta a_\nu}{w} - (h \sin L - k \cos L) \frac{g \Delta a_w}{w} \right], \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{dg}{dt} = \sqrt{\frac{p}{\mu}} \left[-\Delta a_r \cos L + [(w+1) \sin L + g] \frac{\Delta a_\nu}{w} - (h \sin L - k \cos L) \frac{g \Delta a_w}{w} \right], \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{dh}{dt} = \sqrt{\frac{p}{\mu}} \frac{s^2 \Delta a_w}{2w} \cos L, \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{dk}{dt} = \sqrt{\frac{p}{\mu}} \frac{s^2 \Delta a_w}{2w} \sin L, \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{dL}{dt} = \sqrt{\mu p} \left(\frac{w}{p} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{w} \sqrt{\frac{p}{\mu}} (h \sin L - k \cos L) \Delta a_n, \quad (25)$$

where $\alpha^2 = h^2 - k^2$, $s^2 = 1 + h^2 + k^2$, $r = p/w$ and $w = 1 + f \cos L + g \sin L$.

5. Structural analysis

In this section, the structural performance of the tethers of the MEDT system under their mutual bending torque is studied. The stress on the spacecraft-tether joint and the tip displacements of the tethers are argued to be dangerously large for the lengths regime that will be considered for obtaining the Jovian capture, possibly exceeding the material yield strength and causing the entanglement of the tethers, unless appropriate countermeasures are taken. The proposed solution is the addition of transverse dielectric rigid rods. The separation between these rigid rods, L_{bs} , has been calculated to be the maximum distance that prevents the mid-segment points of the tethers from coming into contact.

In the limit where three tethers a , b and c are much longer than their separation, and they stay rigid and parallel with respect to each other at constant distances $d_{ab} = d_{ac} = d_{bc}/2$ (with a being the central tether) the current flowing in each tether, say a , produces a magnetic field that interacts with the current flowing in any other tether, say b , of the MEDT system, resulting in an attractive force per unit length $\frac{dF_b}{dl} = \frac{\mu_0 I_a I_b}{2\pi d_{ab}}$ [see e.g. Ref. 24,

Eq. (5.37) pag. 217]. Therefore, the sum of the attractive electromagnetic forces exerted by the central and external tethers a and c on a segment of length L_s of the other external tether b is

$$F_{bs} = F_{ab} + F_{cb} \approx \frac{\mu_0(2I_a + I_c) I_b}{4\pi d_{ab}} L_s. \quad (26)$$

The total force on tether b due to the current flowing in the other tethers is then $F_b = n_s F_{bs}$, where n_s is the number of segments in b . Eq. (26) can be used to obtain an order of magnitude of the stress and displacement that the tethers are suffering, depending on the values of the currents that can reasonably be achieved for spacecrafts in quasi-parabolic orbit around Jupiter. The resulting upper limit for the lengths of the segments of the tethers, obtained by requiring that the strain does not spoil the structure of the MEDT system, will be an estimate of the appropriate value for the separation between consecutive transverse rigid bars.

Roughly, the order of magnitude of the total torque exerted by the force (26) on a segment of length L_s is

$$\tau_{bs} \approx \frac{1}{2} F_{bs} L_s = \frac{\mu_0(2I_a + I_c) I_b L_s^2}{4\pi d_{ab}}. \quad (27)$$

Here, I_a , I_b and I_c are the average values of the currents flowing in bare tethers moving with velocity v_{rel} relative to the planetary magnetic field \mathbf{B} in the presence of a plasma of electron density N_e , as given in Eq. (2). If the tethers have the same length and diameter, $L_a = L_b = L_c = L_t$, $D_a = D_b = D_c = D$, so that $I_a = I_b = I_c = I_{avg}$, from Eq. (27) we obtain the estimate

$$\tau_{bs} \approx \frac{3\mu_0 I_{avg}^2 L_s^2}{4\pi d_{ab}} \approx 9.0 \times 10^{-14} \times \left[\frac{N \cdot m}{m^6} \right] \times \left(\frac{D^2 L_t^3 L_s^2}{d_{ab}} \right), \quad (28)$$

where Eq. (3) has been taken into account using the value $N_e = 5.4 \cdot 10^9 m^{-3}$ of the electron density of the plasma corresponding to the perijove of the orbit $r_p = 1.1R_J$ that shall be considered in Sec. 9.

The expressions for the direct stress and lateral displacement as functions of the material and its cross section properties can be deduced from bending theory. For simplicity, the rigid tether is modelled as a long beam that resists axial force and bending moment. The material of the tether is considered to be uniform with homogeneous cross-section, and its plane sections are assumed to remain plane after bending. It should be remarked that the last assumption is strictly true only if the bending moment is constant along the beam. If the bending moment changed significantly, shear force would appear, with the corresponding shear stresses. However, when cross-section dimensions are small with respect to the longitudinal length, shear stresses are low and bending theory may be used with reasonable accuracy.

One of the cross-section properties to be calculated is the second moment of area about axes y and z , which are perpendicular to the longitudinal direction of the tether. In case of tethers with a circular cross section of diameter D , this is

$$J_{yy} = \frac{\pi D^4}{64}. \quad (29)$$

Figure 4: Bottom view of the spacecraft, showing the convention for the coordinate axes used in the text.

The scheme of cross section of multitether is shown in Fig. 4. The second moment of area J_{yy} is employed in stress and displacement calculations. The direct stress distribution along the cross section due to bending moment about axis y , M_y , is

$$\sigma_x = \frac{M_y z}{J_{yy}}. \quad (30)$$

In the interaction between two tethers, the non-vanishing bending moment is generated about the perpendicular axis y , M_y , with no orthogonal component ($M_z=0$). As mentioned above, the maximum direct stress on the tether b , $\sigma_{x,max}$, due to the bending torque produced by the current in tether a , $M_y = \tau_{bs}$, will act at the sections placed in the junctions with the rigid transverse bars,

$$\sigma_{x,max} = \frac{\tau_{bs}(D/2)}{J_{yy}} \approx 9.2 \times 10^{-13} \times \left[\frac{N}{m^5} \right] \times \left(\frac{L_t^3 L_s^2}{D d_{ab}} \right). \quad (31)$$

Therefore, yield strength of the material composing the tethers $\sigma_{x,max} < \sigma_{y,mat}$ will limit the expression

$$\frac{L_t^3 L_s^2}{D d_{ab}} < \frac{\sigma_{y,mat}}{9.2 \times 10^{-13} \times [Nm^{-5}]}. \quad (32)$$

For metals, yield strength is, at least, of the order of $2.8 \times 10^8 Nm^{-2}$, so that

$$\frac{L_t^3 L_s^2}{D d_{ab}} = \frac{n_s^3 L_s^5}{D d_{ab}} = \frac{L^5}{n_s^2 D d_{ab}} < 3.1 \times 10^{20} [m^3]. \quad (33)$$

In the case of a titanium alloy Ti-6Al-4V, this upper limit is $9.3 \times 10^{20} m^3$. For titanium, assuming tethers of 9-km-length and 3-mm-diameter, and using 5 transverse bars separated 1800 m, the distance between tethers can be set to a reasonable 0.8 m. To obtain the same 0.8-m tether separation by using an aluminium alloy for the same 9-km-length and 3-mm-diameter tether, the number of transverse bars is 9, and their separation is 1000 m.

Additional constraints may arise from the analysis of the lateral deflection of the tether. The deflection in the midpoint of a simple supported beam (approximation of each tether segment between transverse bars) affected by a punctual force perpendicular to the tether direction, F_{bs} , at the midpoint of the tether segment, is

$$v_{mid} = \frac{F_{bs} L_s^3}{48 E J_{yy}}, \quad (34)$$

where E is Young's modulus, and

$$F_{bs} \approx \frac{2\tau_{bs}}{L_s} \approx 1.8 \times 10^{-13} \times \left[\frac{N}{m^5} \right] \times \left(\frac{D^2 L_t^3 L_s}{d_{ab}} \right). \quad (35)$$

Thus we obtain the estimation,

$$v_{mid} \approx 3.8 \times 10^{-15} \times \left[\frac{N}{m^5} \right] \times \left(\frac{D^2 L_t^3 L_s^4}{d_{ab} E J_{yy}} \right). \quad (36)$$

By substituting a common value of Young's modulus for aluminium, $E = 7 \cdot 10^{10} \frac{N}{m^2}$, the expected lateral displacement is approximately

$$v_{mid} \approx 1.1 \cdot 10^{-24} \times [m^{-3}] \times \left(\frac{L^3 L_s^4}{d_{ab} D^2} \right) \quad (37)$$

In the case of titanium, the constant in Eq. (37) is $6.9 \times 10^{-25} m^{-3}$. Moreover, we can impose in Eq. (37) that midpoint displacement, v_{mid} , is slightly lower than half the distance between tethers, or in the limit $v_{mid} = d_{ab}/2$.

For titanium, assuming tethers of 9-km-length, and 3-mm-diameter, and using 164 transverse bars separated around 55 m, the half the distance between tethers and the lateral tether displacement can be set to a reasonable 0.5 m. We have considered a conservative scenario, because the maximum allowed lateral displacement for the external tether segment midpoint is only half distance between adjacent tethers. Notice that the forces acting on the central tether a due to the two lateral tethers cancel, so that a will not be displaced. To obtain the same 1-m tether separation (or a tether lateral displacement of 0.5 m) by using an aluminium alloy for the same 9-km-length, and 3-mm-diameter, the number of bars is 183, and their separation is 49 m. It can be concluded that the maximum displacement criterion is more critical than the maximum direct stress constraint.

Therefore, the total mass of 6-mm-diameter transverse bars made of a dielectric material as silicon or fiber glass can be estimated from maximum displacement criterion, being the transverse bars-tether mass ratio of 0.05 for aluminium and 0.03 for titanium. Titanium material would be preferred according to structural requirements of the multi-tether configuration.

6. Thermal analysis

The physical interaction with the plasma environment of Jupiter will produce heat and increase the temperature of the EDTs, depending on the tether length, type, and cover. The estimation of the maximum temperature within the tether can be done, first and grossly, by considering the average current along the tether at each time, and, secondly and more accurately, by studying the tether position that reaches maximum temperatures.

As discussed in Ref. [16], the power deposited by the electrons during collection, corresponding to the mechanical power

of the capture, must be equal to the power of the thermal radiation, as described by Stefan–Boltzmann law,

$$(4\varepsilon_t/D)\sigma_B(T_{\text{avg}}^4 - T_{BK}^4)(2\pi r_p/v_{\text{rel}}) = (m_{SC}/m_t)\rho_t v_{\infty}^2, \quad (38)$$

where ε_t is the surface emissivity, σ_B is the Stefan–Boltzmann constant, T_{avg} is the time-and-length averaged tether temperature, T_{BK} is the deep space temperature, D is tether diameter, r_p is the perijove radius, m_{SC} is the spacecraft mass, m_t is the tether mass, ρ_t is the tether material density, and v_{∞} is the arriving velocity. The variables referred to the density and mass of the tether can be used to express the individual tether length in terms of the average tether temperature:

$$L_t = \frac{m_{SC} v_{\infty}^2 v_{\text{rel}}}{2\pi^2 r_p D \sigma_B \varepsilon_t (T_{\text{avg}}^4 - T_{BK}^4)} \quad (39)$$

The mechanical power required for the capture can be divided by the number of tethers used for the capture, n_t , assuming they are identical. Therefore, with the parameters of our project, that is a spacecraft mass of 1000 kg, asymptotic speed of 5.64 km/s (see Sec. 10), perijove at 1.1 radius of Jupiter, $n_t = 3$, tether diameter of 3 mm, and an upper temperature limit due to aluminium fluency of 423 K, the individual tether length needed to radiate the capture energy according to Eq. (39) would be 239 km. This is a conservative method to calculate the tether length because it assumes an average temperature along the tether to reject the energy accumulated during the Jovian capture. However, the real distribution of temperature along the tether will radiate a larger amount of heat to deep space, so a more precise thermal calculation is required, as shown below.

In fact, the variation of the temperature along the tether must be considered to estimate more accurately the maximum temperature and its position along the tether. Following the studies of [16], the derivative of the temperature at a tether position s with respect to tether-to-electric field angle, ϕ , is

$$\frac{\partial \hat{T}}{\partial \phi} = \frac{T_0^3}{T_*^3} \left[\left[2 \cdot \frac{L_t - s}{L_t} \right]^{3/2} |\cos \phi|^{3/2} - \hat{T}^4 \right], \quad (40)$$

where

$$T_0^4 = \frac{N_e q_e v_s B_s L_t}{2\varepsilon_t \pi \sigma_B} \sqrt{\frac{q_e v_s B_s L_t}{m_e}} F_2(\hat{r}_M) [F_1(\hat{r}_M)]^{3/4}, \quad (41)$$

where \hat{r}_M is the radius normalized with its minimum (perijove) value, v_s is the parabolic velocity, B_s is the magnetic intensity coefficient of Jupiter's magnetic field as a no-tilt no-offset dipole, and

$$T_*^3 = \frac{\rho_t c_t \omega_t D}{4\varepsilon_t \sigma_B}. \quad (42)$$

In Eq. 41, the functions $F_1(\hat{r}_M)$ and $F_2(\hat{r}_M)$ are

$$F_1(\hat{r}_M) = \left(\frac{\hat{r}_M^{7/3} - \hat{r}_M^{4/3}}{2^{7/6}} \right)^2, \quad (43)$$

$$F_2(\hat{r}_M) = f_N \exp(2.72 \hat{r}_M^{2/3} - 3.43). \quad (44)$$

Extreme values of the non-dimensional temperature, $\hat{T} = T/T_0$, along the capture motion occur when the derivative (40) vanishes. Moreover, the maximum temperature along the tether is reached in the perijove, $\phi = 0$, and at the end position $s = 0$,

$$\hat{T}_{\text{max}} = 2^{3/2}. \quad (45)$$

Aluminium and titanium are investigated as bulk materials for calculating the maximum tether length, considering their fluency temperatures. In the case of aluminium, the length should not exceed 1065 m for the tether to be below 423 K. For titanium, the length can be 9150 m to be below 900 K. Therefore, titanium will be chosen to improve the thermal and structural performance of the tethers.

7. Choice of the configuration

The relativistic, thermal and structural constraints discussed in Sections 3, 5, and 6, imply that EDTs as large as 20 or 50 km, as required for obtaining self-propelled orbit insertion [12, 13], would not survive the impact with Jupiter's plasma-magnetosphere. As shown in Sec. 6, the maximum allowed tether length is ~ 9.2 km for titanium, or ~ 1 km for aluminum, values that are far from being sufficient for generating the acceleration required for the capture. This limitation can be circumvented by using multiple tethers. Even if each of them is chosen to be shorter than the 9.2 km limit, their Lorentz forces can sum up and lead to the capture.

With these motivations, we will consider a MEDT self-propelled vehicle of total mass 1000 kg, using three Titanium tethers of 9-km-length and 3-mm-diameter. The payload for the control and scientific instruments can be around 150 kg, similar to that of Galileo satellite [25]. Such a system is compatible with all the structural, thermal, and relativistic constraints discussed above. The vehicle is assumed to be aligned in nadir pointing direction as in Fig. 4. This configuration will be shown to allow for obtaining self-propelled capture and power generation for the scientific instruments once the target orbit is reached. Moreover, the MEDT would also contribute to the attitude control through gravity gradient stabilization, and could be used as a heater for the thermal subsystem.

8. Initial conditions

To characterize the initial hyperbolic orbit, three choices are required: the orbital plane; the distance at perijove; and the arrival velocity v_{∞} , or equivalently the eccentricity.

Like in [13], an equatorial orbit will be chosen in order to maximize the effect of the MEDT. The distance at perijove is set to be $1.1R_J$, as for the Radio Telescope Mission described in [26]. Such a close orbit may also allow for a detailed observation of the surface of the planet. The arrival velocity v_{∞} defines the eccentricity of the incoming hyperbola, as seen in Jupiter's

system of reference. In Ref. [11], an ideal Hohmann interplanetary transfer was described with $v_\infty \approx 5.64$ km/s while in [16] and [26] higher velocities such as 6 km/s and 6.854 km/s were considered. Here, the selected asymptotic velocity is $v_\infty = 5.924$ km/s, which corresponds to a characteristic energy [e.g. 20, page 104] $C_3 = v_\infty^2 = 35.09$ km²/s² and an eccentricity $e = 1 + \frac{v_\infty^2 p}{\mu} = 1.0197$. This value was obtained as output of the designed interplanetary transfer which will be fully described in Sec. 10.

An estimation of an appropriate time span of propagation for the numerical integration of Gauss variational equations can be obtained from the analytical relation between the hyperbolic mean anomaly M_h and the true anomaly ν for the unperturbed problem,

$$M_h \equiv \frac{h}{p^2} (e^2 - 1)^{\frac{3}{2}} (t - t_p) = -\ln \left(\frac{\sqrt{e+1} + \sqrt{e-1} \tan \frac{\nu}{2}}{\sqrt{e+1} - \sqrt{e-1} \tan \frac{\nu}{2}} \right) + \frac{e \sqrt{e^2 - 1} \sin \nu}{1 + e \cos \nu}. \quad (46)$$

For a hyperbolic trajectory, $-v_\infty < \nu < v_\infty$, with $v_\infty = \arccos(-1/e)$. A good choice of a finite time span can then be that corresponding to initial and final values of the true anomalies $\nu_1 = -0.99 v_\infty$ and $\nu_2 = 0.99 v_\infty$, in such a way that a significant part of the evolution is considered. The time between these two asymptotic positions of the unperturbed trajectory is,

$$t = \frac{(M_{h2} - M_{h1}) p^2}{(e^2 - 1)^{\frac{3}{2}} h}. \quad (47)$$

For the given values of the eccentricity and perijove of the orbit, this corresponds to a time span $\Delta t = 6.49 \times 10^6$ s ≈ 75 days. As shall be seen, this choice of the time span for the simulation is also sufficient for appreciating the effect of the perturbing MEDT acceleration. Finally, the tether will be assumed to optimally oriented all the time (nadir pointing). Although a detailed attitude dynamics study is beyond the scope of this work, we notice that such a radial orientation is favored by the gravity gradient stabilization due to the long MEDTs, thus it may be realistically maintained with minimal control requirements.

9. Orbit insertion and circularization

Since the initial position and velocity lie in the equatorial plane of the magnetic field, corresponding to vanishing inclination, $i = 0$ in Eq. (10), the orthogonal component of the Lorentz force \mathbf{F}_L along the axis $\hat{\mathbf{w}}$ vanishes. Therefore, the vehicle will remain in the equatorial plane. Taking into account that \mathbf{F}_L , as given in Eq. (10), has no component along the $\hat{\mathbf{r}}$ direction, it can be seen that the effect of the EDT on an equatorial orbit is the term proportional to $\hat{\mathbf{v}}$ in Eq. (10). This produces a deceleration that can be used to reduce the eccentricity of the orbit, eventually reaching a value lower than 1, corresponding to the achievement of the orbital insertion.

Fig. 5 shows the numerical solution of Gauss variational equations, Eqs. (20) to (25), with the initial conditions discussed in section 8. Although the simulation was performed using the non-singular equinoctial variables, for convenience the results are given for the classical orbital elements that show a significant variation. The main effect of the MEDT self-propulsion is a sharp reduction of the eccentricity and the specific angular momentum, which also result in a reduction of the linear velocity of the spacecraft. These changes occur around the midpoint of the simulation, corresponding to the perijove of the incoming hyperbolic trajectory, like for an impulsive maneuver.

Figure 5: Variation of the specific angular momentum (top) and eccentricity (bottom) during the insertion.

In particular, the eccentricity decreases to the value 0.995, thus the trajectory of the spacecraft becomes elliptical. In other words, the initial conditions that have been considered allow for obtaining the orbital insertion due to the MEDT self-propulsion. The effect on the other orbital elements is either small or not significant.

Figs. 6, 7 and 8 show the results of the integration of Gauss variational equations with the same initial conditions, but with a longer simulation time, namely 220 days. It can be seen that the osculating eccentricity decreases steadily, leading to a nearly circular orbit after a few turns. The effect of the MEDT is important the closer the satellite is to Jupiter. This occurs around the periapsis of the elliptical orbits when the eccentricity is still high. Interestingly, during the first few turns, the satellite would also cross the orbits of several Galilean moons. After the circularization is completed, the deceleration is important during the entire orbits, and it would make the satellite spiral down into the atmosphere of the planet. This undesired effect can be avoided by retracting or ejecting the tether after the target circular orbit is obtained.

Figure 6: Detail of the trajectory of the spacecraft in the orbital plane. The orbits of the Galilean moons are also shown for comparison. The moons are listed in the legend in an order corresponding to increasing distance from Jupiter.

Figure 7: Evolution of the eccentricity and the adimensional distance from the center of Jupiter during the first 220 days after reaching Jovian SOI.

However, a more interesting possibility would be to switch the operating mode of the MEDT, by connecting a load of electric resistance R in series to each tether, in the way to the cathode. This would result in a reduction of the current, which would become

$$I = \frac{\Phi}{R + R_L} \approx \frac{v_{\text{rel}} B L_t}{R}, \quad (48)$$

assuming that $R \gg R_L = \rho L_t / A$, where R_L is the resistance of each tether, $A = \pi D^2 / 4$ is its cross section, and $\rho = 420 \text{ n}\Omega \cdot \text{m}$ is the electrical resistivity of Titanium. This regime is obtained if $R \gg R_L = 535 \Omega$, for tethers of length $L_t = 9 \text{ km}$ and diameter $D = 3 \text{ mm}$.

The option of keeping the MEDT with reduced current even after the target orbit is reached would imply two important advantages. First, the MEDT could be used for attitude control by gravity-gradient stabilization, as in Refs. [27, 28], in which tethers have been proposed for attitude control of orbits around the earth.

Second, the remaining current flowing in the load R could be used to feed the power necessities of the scientific payload of the vehicle [29]. Taking into account the three tethers, the available power would be

$$P = 3R \frac{\Phi^2}{(R + R_L)^2} \approx 3 \frac{v_{\text{rel}}^2 B^2 L_t^2}{R}. \quad (49)$$

As an example, a power $P = 3 \text{ kW}$ could be obtained by choos-

Figure 8: Evolution of the average current and Lorentz force in the tether during the first 220 days after reaching Jovian SOI.

ing $R = 3 \frac{v_{\text{rel}}^2 B^2 L_t^2}{P} \approx 346 \text{ K}\Omega$, for the orbit at distance $1.1 R_J$ from the center of the planet. With this choice of R , the current flowing in each tether, as given in Eq. (48), would drop by a factor $\sim 6.5 \times 10^2$. Table 1 gives an estimate of the lifetime before deorbiting corresponding to different choices of the instant in which the resistance R is switched on along the trajectory given in Figs. 6 and 7, thus modifying the subsequent trajectory. For simplicity, this instant is chosen to coincide with one of the apojove passes of the trajectory of Fig. 6. It can be seen that the mission can last for a few decades after the capture, depending on the instant in which the switch is applied.

Pass	r_a/R_J	Switch time [days]	Deorbit time [years]	Mission lifetime [years]
1	218.9	37.62	>60	>60
2	85.51	173.61	>60	>60
3	29.45	202.55	>40	>40
4	20.09	206.02	26.95	29.91
6	11.47	208.33	16.43	19.39
8	7.99	216.44	10.78	13.74
12	4.61	222.22	5.07	8.03
14	3.58	223.38	3.17	6.13

Table 1: Total mission lifetime (last column) including the interplanetary transfer, depending on the time (third column) and pass (first column) at which the resistance R is switched on along the trajectory described in Fig. 6. The switch is operated at the apojove distance indicated in column 2. After the switch, the trajectory still spirals down, but at a lower pace than in Fig. 6. Eventually, deorbiting is expected to occur around the time (counted after the capture) shown in the fourth column.

Most of the power generated by the MEDT system will be supplied in the parts of the orbit in which the spacecraft is nearer to the planet. In order to provide a constant power, e.g. of 1 kW , part of the 3 kW of power obtained around each perijove pass could be stored in a battery system.

10. Transfer to Jupiter

The results presented in Sec. 9 have been obtained by studying the movement of the MEDT satellite within the Sphere of

Influence (SOI) of Jupiter. This SOI, corresponding to distances from the center of Jupiter in the range $r < 687R_J$, has to be reached with an interplanetary transfer from the Earth. While past missions reached Jupiter performing multiple gravity-assist maneuvers with chemical propulsion, here a direct transfer orbit will be considered to avoid any additional on-board propulsion system besides the MEDT.

The optimal launch epoch in this decade has been evaluated by minimizing the characteristic energy, C_3 , for both the departure and arrival hyperbolic orbits. A lower C_3 at departure reduces the required capabilities of the launcher, while a lower C_3 at the arrival implies smaller values for the incoming velocity with respect to Jupiter, thus reducing the number of tethers needed for the capture.

Fig. 9 shows the values of the arrival velocity at Jupiter’s SOI and the duration of the planetary transfer that can be obtained depending on the departure epoch. It can be seen that the difference of the orbital periods of the Earth and Jupiter implies the existence of an almost optimal launch per year.

Figure 9: Arrival velocity v_∞ (in contour levels) relative to Jupiter’s SOI, as a function of the interplanetary transfer duration and the departure epoch.

The optimal launch of the decade, in terms of total C_3 energy, corresponds to the launch epoch of 24 December of 2028 with a transfer time of 2.96 years and an outgoing C_3 energy of $75.802 \text{ km}^2/\text{s}^2$. The corresponding arrival velocity in Jupiter’s reference frame is 5.64 km/s . These energy requirements for a 1 ton payload can be met with launchers such as Atlas V and Delta IV [30].

Fig. 10 shows the interplanetary phase, taking into account the inclination between both planets. The interplanetary transfer design was performed using an optimizer of the Lambert’s problem based in [31]. The simulation ends when the satellite enters the SOI of Jupiter. Its subsequent evolution with MEDT self-propulsion results in the trajectory that has been studied in Sec. 9, producing the capture and eventually leading to the target orbit around Jupiter.

Figure 10: Interplanetary trajectory corresponding to the optimal launch window, represented in the J2000 reference frame.

11. Conclusions

We have presented a comprehensive analysis of the structural, thermal, and relativistic constraints for the operation of electrodynamic tethers for self propulsion in Jupiter’s environment. These limits rule out the proposals of using single tethers of 20 to 50 km length for obtaining Jovian capture that have been discussed in the literature. The result for the maximum allowed tether length is $\sim 9.2 \text{ km}$ for titanium, or $\sim 1 \text{ km}$ for aluminium, values that are far from being sufficient for generating the acceleration required for the capture using a single tether.

We have shown that these limitations can be circumvented by using multiple electrodynamic tethers (MEDT) of shorter length. In particular, we have considered a system of three titanium tethers of 9-km-length and 3-mm diameter, and shown how it can fulfill all the structural, thermal, and relativistic requirements. Moreover, our simulations show that the combined Lorentz forces of such MEDT system in Jupiter’s plasma-magnetosphere are sufficient to lead to the capture of a spacecraft of a total mass of 1000 kg. The Jovian insertion and the subsequent evolution of the self-propelled vehicle around the planet have been studied with Gauss variational equations using non-singular modified equinoctial elements, and taking into account an accurate modeling of the electron density of Jupiter’s environment.

We have also analyzed the previous interplanetary transfer, and selected an optimal solution to Lambert’s problem, indicating the appropriate launch window in the next decade. This direct transfer, affordable with current launchers capabilities, ensures that the spacecraft does not need any additional propulsive system besides the MEDT for reaching Jupiter and obtaining the desired orbit insertion. As a result, a payload mass similar to Galileo’s could be set in orbit around Jupiter with a considerable reduction in launch mass. Moreover, the MEDT would also contribute to the attitude control through gravity gradient stabilization, and could be used for power generation after the capture, at an average rate around 1 kW for reasonable choices of the parameters.

This work may be used as a baseline for future missions to Jupiter or to the Galilean moons using non conventional propul-

sion systems.

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